

Efficient Energy Management in a Hybrid Microgrid Using Solar, Wind, Battery, and Supercapacitor for AC/DC Loads and EV Charging Application

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Hybrid Microgrid, Energy Management System (EMS), Solar, Wind, Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG), Incremental Conductance (INC) MPPT, Battery, Supercapacitor, Bidirectional Buck-Boost Converter, AC/DC Loads, Electric Vehicle (EV) Charging	This paper presents the design and simulation of an advanced Energy Management System for a high-capacity hybrid microgrid that integrates solar and wind energy sources with battery and supercapacitor storage. The proposed system is an enhancement of previous small-scale models, developed to support long-term and large-scale applications including AC and DC loads along with Electric Vehicle charging infrastructure. Solar energy is harvested using a boost converter operated with the Incremental Conductance Maximum Power Point Tracking algorithm to ensure maximum power extraction under varying environmental conditions. Wind energy is generated through a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator, with its AC output converted to DC using a diode bridge rectifier followed by a DC to DC boost converter for efficient power optimization. Both renewable sources are connected to a common DC bus to maintain voltage stability and continuous energy flow. The energy storage system combines batteries and supercapacitors managed by a bidirectional buck-boost converter, which facilitates dynamic charging and discharging operations. A double loop control strategy consisting of voltage and current control is applied to ensure reliable power delivery and balance between supply and demand in response to fluctuating renewable generation. The Energy Management System effectively

coordinates the operation of energy sources, storage components, and connected loads including Electric Vehicle chargers, thereby improving system efficiency, reliability, and performance. The entire system is modeled and simulated in MATLAB Simulink, and the results confirm its capability to maintain stable operation under variable environmental and load conditions.

I. Introduction

The growing global concern over climate change and fossil fuel depletion has led to a paradigm shift toward cleaner, more sustainable energy systems. Hybrid microgrids, which integrate multiple renewable energy sources with energy storage systems, have become a promising solution for ensuring energy security, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and supporting distributed generation [1], [2]. These systems can operate either in grid-connected mode or as standalone systems, providing reliable power supply to remote or isolated areas where conventional grid extension is economically or technically infeasible [3]. Standalone hybrid microgrids find application in a wide range of settings, such as rural electrification, islanded communities, military forward operating bases, disaster relief zones, mobile charging stations, and off-grid commercial and industrial sites [4], [5]. These applications demand a robust and adaptive energy management system (EMS) capable of coordinating energy generation, storage, and consumption in real time to meet dynamic load profiles while maintaining power quality and reliability. Solar and wind energy have emerged as the most viable renewable sources for standalone systems due to their availability and technological maturity. Solar photovoltaic (PV) modules provide energy during daylight hours, while wind turbines can generate power throughout the day, complementing solar output and enhancing the overall reliability of the system [6]. However, both resources are inherently variable and unpredictable due to changing weather conditions, making energy storage an essential component of any standalone system [7]. Batteries are the most widely used storage technology due to their ability to store significant amounts of energy for long durations. However, batteries alone may not meet the fast-response power demands of fluctuating loads or sudden dips in renewable generation. Supercapacitors, with their high power density and rapid charge/discharge capabilities, are ideal for addressing such short-term dynamics and reducing stress on batteries [8], [9]. A hybrid energy storage system that combines batteries and

supercapacitors can thus ensure both energy and power balance, improve overall efficiency, and extend battery life [10]. In this context, an efficient energy management system becomes crucial. The EMS coordinates power flows between the renewable sources, battery-supercapacitor storage, and loads, while ensuring stable operation of the microgrid. The EMS also enables optimal power dispatch, state of charge (SOC) monitoring, load prioritization, and fault tolerance in standalone mode [11], [12]. For solar energy harvesting, DC-DC boost converters are used along with Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms. Among these, the Incremental Conductance (INC) method is preferred due to its higher accuracy and faster convergence under rapidly changing irradiance conditions [13]. Wind energy is captured using Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generators (PMSGs), which are known for their compact size, high efficiency, and direct-drive capability. The generated AC power is converted to DC using a diode bridge rectifier followed by a boost converter to ensure voltage regulation and power optimization [14], [15]. The integration of energy storage is facilitated using bidirectional buck-boost converters, which allow seamless charging and discharging based on power availability and load requirements. A double-loop control strategy, comprising an outer voltage loop and an inner current loop, is implemented to manage the dynamic behavior of the energy storage system and to maintain DC bus voltage stability [16], [17]. Standalone hybrid microgrids are also increasingly being designed to support AC and DC loads, including Electric Vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure, which introduces high-power, time-variable demands on the system [18]. The integration of EV charging in standalone microgrids supports decentralized transport electrification, especially in regions where grid access is limited or unreliable [19], [20]. Recent studies have explored the effectiveness of advanced control techniques and intelligent EMS in standalone systems. Reference [21] showed how coordinated control of hybrid energy sources and energy storage enhances the reliability and performance of rural microgrids.

Reference [22] analyzed the impact of EV charging on residential systems, emphasizing the importance of adaptive EMS in standalone environments. Simulation tools such as MATLAB/Simulink are widely used to model, analyze, and validate the performance of hybrid microgrid components under realistic environmental and load conditions [23], [24]. Despite significant progress, many existing systems are either small-scale or lack integration of advanced energy storage solutions such as supercapacitors. Moreover, comprehensive standalone microgrids with coordinated control for diverse load profiles including AC, DC, and EV loads remain an active research area [25]. This paper addresses these gaps by proposing a MATLAB/Simulink-based design and simulation of an advanced standalone hybrid microgrid integrating solar, wind, battery, and supercapacitor storage. The system is designed to serve AC and DC loads, along with EV charging infrastructure, using a coordinated energy management system for efficient and reliable operation under varying environmental and load conditions.

2. System Configuration

The proposed standalone hybrid microgrid integrates solar and wind energy sources with a hybrid energy storage system comprising batteries and supercapacitors to supply both AC and DC loads, including electric

vehicle (EV) charging stations as shown in Fig.1. A photovoltaic (PV) array is connected to a boost converter controlled by an Incremental Conductance (INC) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm, which ensures maximum power extraction under changing environmental conditions. Wind energy is harvested using a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG), whose three-phase AC output is rectified by a diode bridge rectifier and then boosted through a DC-DC converter to stabilize the voltage. Both renewable sources feed into a common DC bus that maintains system voltage and supports load flexibility. The battery and supercapacitor are connected to the DC bus through a bidirectional buck-boost converter, enabling charge and discharge operations depending on power availability and demand. A double-loop voltage and current control strategy is used to regulate the energy flow and maintain system stability. AC loads are powered through a DC-AC inverter, while DC loads and EV chargers are directly supplied from the DC bus. An Energy Management System (EMS) monitors generation, storage state-of-charge, and load conditions, making real-time decisions to optimize power sharing among sources and ensure reliable supply. This configuration supports autonomous operation in remote or off-grid areas and is well suited for high-capacity energy systems requiring sustainable and stable performance.

Fig.1 proposed system configuration for EMS

III. Integrated Renewable Energy System and Hybrid Energy Storage for EV Charging and Load Support

This concept describes the modeling, operation, and control of a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system incorporating solar PV, wind energy via PMSG, a hybrid battery-supercapacitor energy storage system, and electric vehicle (EV) charging, all interconnected via a common DC bus and managed by a central Energy Management System (EMS). The system is simulated in MATLAB/Simulink to verify performance under varying environmental and load conditions.

A. Solar PV System Operation and Modeling

The solar photovoltaic (PV) array converts solar irradiance into DC electrical power. The output of a PV module is nonlinear and depends on irradiance and temperature. The output current of a PV cell is mathematically modeled by:

Fig. 2 equivalent model of PV solar.

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{nkT}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- I_{ph} = photo-generated current
- I_0 = reverse saturation current of the diode
- q = charge of an electron (1.6×10^{-19} C)
- n = diode ideality factor
- k = Boltzmann constant (1.38×10^{-23} J/K)
- T = cell temperature in Kelvin
- R_s, R_{sh} = series and shunt resistances respectively

To extract maximum power, a boost converter is connected at the PV output and controlled using the Incremental Conductance (INC) MPPT algorithm, which adjusts the duty cycle D based on equation (2) as shown in Fig.3:

$$V_{out} = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3 solar PV INC MPPT DC-DC boost converter

The INC method compares incremental conductance dI/dV with instantaneous conductance I/V to track the Maximum Power Point (MPP) under varying irradiance conditions as shown in Fig.4.

Fig. 4. Flow chart of INC algorithm of MPPT for solar conversion.

B. Wind Energy System Operation and PMSG Modeling

The wind subsystem uses a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG) connected to a wind turbine to convert kinetic wind energy into electrical energy. The mechanical power from wind is given by:

$$P_{wind} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_p(\lambda, \beta) V_w^3 \quad (3)$$

Where:

- ρ = air density (kg/m^3)
- A = swept area of the turbine blades
- $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ = power coefficient as a function of tip-speed ratio λ and pitch angle β
- V_w = wind speed (m/s)

The PMSG's dq-axis voltage equations in the rotating reference frame are:

$$V_d = R_s i_d + L_d \frac{di_d}{dt} + \omega_e L_q i_q \quad (4)$$

$$V_q = R_s i_q + L_q \frac{di_q}{dt} + \omega_e L_d i_d + \omega_e \lambda_m \quad (5)$$

Where:

- V_d, V_q : d- and q-axis voltages
- i_d, i_q : d- and q-axis currents
- L_d, L_q : inductances in d and q axes
- ω_e : electrical angular velocity
- λ_m : permanent magnet flux linkage
- R_s : stator resistance

The AC output is rectified using a diode bridge, and a boost converter regulates the DC link voltage as shown in Fig.5:

Fig. 5 wind energy conversion system with INC MPPT DC-DC boost converter

$$V_{dc} = \frac{V_{rect}}{1-D} \quad (6)$$

The boost converter maintains power balance by adjusting the duty cycle based on DC bus voltage feedback as shown in Fig.6.

Fig. 6. Flow chart of INC algorithm of MPPT for wind conversion.

C. Common DC Bus Operation and Control

The common DC bus interconnects all sources and loads. Its voltage is regulated by adjusting the duty cycles of the interfacing converters to maintain energy balance as shown in Fig.7 and 8:

$$\sum P_{sources} = \sum P_{loads} + \sum P_{loss} + \frac{d}{dt}(E_{storage}) \quad (7)$$

Control is implemented via a double-loop control mechanism:

Fig. 7 Proposed energy management strategy for the BESS

Fig. 8 Proposed energy management strategy for the Supercapacitor

Outer voltage loop (PI controller):

$$I_{ref}(t) = K_{pv} (V_{ref} - V_{dc}(t)) + K_{iv} \int (V_{ref} - V_{dc}(t)) dt \quad (8)$$

(8)

Inner current loop:

$$D(t) = K_{pc} (I_{ref}(t) - I_{actual}(t)) + K_{ic} \int (I_{ref}(t) - I_{actual}(t)) dt \quad (9)$$

(9)

This ensures quick dynamic response and stable bus voltage under varying load and generation scenarios.

D. Hybrid Energy Storage System (Battery + Supercapacitor)

The energy storage system in the hybrid microgrid consists of a battery and a supercapacitor, both connected through a bidirectional buck-boost converter. The battery stores energy for long durations, while the supercapacitor handles rapid fluctuations in load demand due to its fast response capability as shown in Fig.9 and 10. During periods of excess renewable generation, the converter charges the battery and supercapacitor. When the load increases or generation drops, it discharges energy to support the system. A state-of-charge-based control algorithm manages the operation. If the battery's charge is above 80 percent, it stores surplus energy. If it drops below 30 percent, the battery is preserved, and the supercapacitor supplies energy. This setup ensures efficient energy flow, stable voltage, and reliable system performance.

The energy storage system includes:

- A battery for long-duration energy storage
- A supercapacitor for fast transient response

A bidirectional buck-boost converter connects each storage unit:

$$\text{Buck Mode (discharging): } V_{out} = D \cdot V_{in} \quad (10)$$

Boost Mode (charging): $V_{out} = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D}$ (11)

Fig.9 bidirectional dc-dc buck boost converter BESS
The supercapacitor energy is given by:

Fig.10 Super capacitor banks

$$E = \frac{1}{2}C(V_{max}^2 - V_{min}^2) \quad (12)$$

A state-of-charge (SOC)-based algorithm manages charging/discharging:

- If $SOC_{battery} > 80\%$, battery stores excess energy.
- If $SOC_{battery} < 30\%$, battery is protected and supercapacitor delivers power.

This division enhances lifespan and efficiency.

E. Inverter operation for AC load

In a DC grid-based renewable energy system, the inverter is crucial for supplying AC loads. After generating electrical energy from sources like solar panels and wind turbines, it is converted into AC using a Voltage Source Inverter (VSI). The VSI uses semiconductor switches, typically IGBTs, in single-phase or three-phase full-bridge configurations. The switching operation is controlled through Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) techniques, most commonly Sinusoidal PWM (SPWM), to generate an AC voltage waveform resembling a sinusoidal signal as shown in Fig.11. The resulting waveform contains high-frequency harmonics, which are filtered out using an LC low-pass filter to produce a clean AC output suitable for household or industrial loads. This inverter allows for seamless integration of renewable DC power into AC applications

while maintaining voltage stability, frequency accuracy, and load compatibility.

Fig.11 inverter Conversion design for AC load

Fig.12 Inverter controller

$$V_{AC} = m \cdot V_{dc} \quad (13)$$

Where m is the modulation index.

F. EV-Based Backup Power Support for AC and DC Applications

The islanded DC microgrid system uses an electric vehicle (EV) battery as a power source for both AC and DC loads during discharge conditions. This is achieved through a DC-DC bidirectional buck-boost converter, which boosts the EV battery voltage to maintain the required DC link level. For AC loads, the boosted voltage is processed by a DC-AC inverter, converting the regulated DC power into AC form suitable for household appliances as shown in Fig.13. This configuration allows the EV to act as a backup energy source during periods of low renewable generation or unexpected load demand. The bidirectional converter ensures efficient power flow, while the double-loop controller maintains voltage stability and prevents battery over-discharge, making the EV a reliable support element for powering both AC and DC loads in the standalone microgrid.

Fig.13 bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter for EV charging system

G. Energy Management System (EMS)

The EMS supervises the hybrid system using real-time measurements of:

- P_{gen} : power generated from PV and wind
- P_{load} : load demand
- SOC: state of charge of battery and supercapacitor

The EMS ensures system stability and optimal performance by:

- Maximizing renewable energy usage
- Maintaining power balance:

$$P_{gen} + P_{battery} + P_{sc} = P_{load} + P_{EV} + P_{loss} \quad (14)$$

IV. Simulation Results and Discussions

A. Dynamic Solar Irradiance Profile During Simulation

The proposed hybrid microgrid system was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink with a total run time of 2 seconds to evaluate its performance under dynamic operating conditions. Solar irradiance started at 1000 W/m^2 and was reduced to 500 W/m^2 between 0.2 seconds and 0.8 seconds to simulate partial shading. This reduction led to a temporary drop in solar power generation, during which the battery system began discharging, as shown in Fig. 14, to compensate for the deficit and maintain a stable DC bus voltage. The supercapacitor responded to rapid transients, ensuring smooth voltage support during switching and load variations. Simultaneously, Electric Vehicle (EV) charging was active and continued without interruption, drawing power from the common DC bus. The Energy Management System prioritized the load and charging requirements by balancing input from wind generation and storage devices. Despite the drop in solar availability, the system sustained reliable operation and delivered continuous power to all connected AC/DC loads and EV chargers. These results confirm the robustness of the proposed energy management strategy and its ability to maintain stable operation under varying environmental and load conditions.

Fig.14 Simulation results of Solar Irradiation Transitions and Energy Management

B. Dynamic Behavior of wind power generation During Wind Speed changes

The simulation was run for 2 seconds to evaluate the system performance under changing wind conditions. From 0.9 seconds to 1.2 seconds, the wind speed decreases from 12 m/s to 8 m/s, causing a reduction in the power generated by the wind turbine and the Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator as shown in Fig.15. As a result, the DC voltage at the common bus tends to drop. To maintain stable operation, the Energy Management System adjusts the boost converter duty cycle and engages the battery and supercapacitor storage units to supply the deficit power. The battery discharges gradually while the supercapacitor provides quick bursts of power to stabilize voltage fluctuations. The double-loop control with voltage and current regulation ensures the DC bus voltage remains steady, delivering reliable power to both AC/DC loads and Electric Vehicle chargers. The simulation confirms that the system effectively manages energy flow during wind speed decreases, maintaining continuous power supply and overall system stability.

Fig.15 simulation results of Dynamic Wind Profile and Hybrid Microgrid Performance

C. EV Charging under Renewable Energy Deficiency and Battery Backup

The simulation is run for a total duration of 2 seconds. Electric Vehicle (EV) charging begins at 1.5 seconds and continues until 1.85 seconds, with the charging current gradually increasing from 0 A to 25 A. During this period, renewable energy sources such as solar and wind do not generate power due to low environmental conditions as shown in Fig.16. As a result, the battery storage system acts as the primary power supplier, providing the necessary backup energy to maintain continuous EV charging. Meanwhile, both AC and DC loads continue to receive stable power without interruption. This demonstrates the system's ability to seamlessly manage energy flows and prioritize critical loads, ensuring reliable EV charging even when renewable generation is temporarily unavailable.

Fig.16 simulation results of EV charging condition and its performance

D. Significance and Regulation of DC Bus Voltage (V_{dc}) in a Hybrid Microgrid

In a hybrid microgrid system, V_{dc} represents the DC bus voltage, which is the central voltage level maintained across the DC-link capacitor that connects various system components such as solar panels, wind turbines, batteries, supercapacitors, EV chargers, and power converters. This voltage acts as a common electrical point where power from different sources is collected and distributed to various loads. Maintaining a constant V_{dc} is essential for ensuring stable and efficient operation of the system, as it directly affects the performance of DC-DC and DC-AC converters. Any fluctuation in renewable power generation or load demand can cause deviations in V_{dc} , which are

corrected in real-time by the energy management controller through coordinated charging and discharging of the battery and supercapacitor. A well-regulated DC bus voltage ensures smooth energy flow, uninterrupted EV charging, and reliable power supply to both AC and DC loads under dynamic operating conditions.

Fig. 17 simulation results and Dynamic Analysis of EV Charging in Hybrid Microgrid system

E. Dynamic Performance of Hybrid Microgrid under Solar Irradiance Variation, Wind Speed Fluctuation, and EV Charging Demand

The simulation runs for a total duration of 2 seconds to analyze the hybrid microgrid's performance under varying conditions. Solar irradiance decreases from 1000 W/m^2 to 500 W/m^2 between 0.2 seconds and 0.8 seconds, causing a corresponding reduction in solar power output. During this period, the battery storage system discharges to compensate for the shortfall, maintaining a reliable supply to AC and DC loads. Wind speed undergoes a decrease from 12 m/s to 8 m/s between 0.9 seconds and 1.2 seconds, leading to reduced wind power generation. The battery and supercapacitor work together to support the load demand and stabilize the DC bus voltage during this fluctuation. Electric Vehicle (EV) charging starts at 1.5 seconds and continues until 1.85 seconds, with charging current increasing from 0 A to 25 A. At this time, solar and wind generation are minimal due to environmental conditions.

Consequently, the battery system provides the necessary backup power to support EV charging along with other connected loads, ensuring uninterrupted operation. Overall, the Energy Management System effectively balances generation, storage, and load demands under

these dynamic conditions, demonstrating stable voltage regulation and continuous power delivery throughout the simulation period.

Fig.18 Simulation Results of Hybrid Microgrid under Dynamic Solar, Wind, and EV Charging Conditions

V. Conclusion

This work presents an efficient and scalable hybrid microgrid system that integrates solar and wind energy sources with battery and supercapacitor storage for powering AC/DC loads and Electric Vehicle charging infrastructure. The use of an Incremental Conductance-based MPPT controller for the PV system and a boost converter for wind energy ensures optimal power extraction. The integration of a common DC bus with a double-loop voltage and current control using PI controllers maintains voltage stability and dynamic power sharing among sources and loads. The bidirectional buck-boost converter effectively manages the charging and discharging operations of the hybrid storage system, ensuring fast response and long-term energy backup. The Energy Management System plays a key role in coordinating the operation of all subsystems, achieving power balance and high reliability. MATLAB/Simulink simulations validate that the system performs reliably under varying solar irradiance, wind speeds, and load demands, making it a suitable solution for modern, clean energy-based infrastructure.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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